

EU4ADVICE Network of Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) advisors in Europe

4 LIVING LABS

**Empower
producers
and
consumers**

Short food supply chains (SFSC) are a mean for both producers and consumers providing choices to gain better positions in the value chain, improving trust, transparency, food quality and safety.

**Connecting
SFSC-
advisors**

Bolster SFSC-related advisory services to chain actors, to help them make their practices more economically, socially and environmentally sustainable, connecting SFSC-advisors from the 27 member States in a common network.

**Integration
into AKIS
governance**

Integration of SFSC advisors and content into national AKIS and interaction with policy makers at national, regional and local levels with the intention of identifying barriers and working towards improved policies and regulations.

**Pooling
contents
and
training
materials**

Providing specific training materials, guides, contents, good practices, workshops, seminars and discussion fori to SFSC advisors.

Coordinator Partner

Partners

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